

Supporting Information

Triplet-Triplet Annihilation Upconversion by Polymeric Sensitizers

Keshav Kumar Jha^{ab}, Amrutha Prabhakaran^c, Christopher S. Burke^c, Marcus Schulze^{de}, Ulrich S. Schubert^{df}, Tia E. Keyes^c, Michael Jäger^{df}, Benjamin Dietzek Ivanšić^{*ab}

^aLeibniz Institute of Photonic Technology Jena, Research Department Functional Interfaces, Albert-Einstein-Straße 9, 07745 Jena, Germany.

^bInstitute of Physical Chemistry and Abbe Center of Photonics, Friedrich Schiller University Jena, Helmholtzweg 4, 07743 Jena, Germany.

^cSchool of Chemical Sciences, National Centre for Sensor Research, Dublin City University, Dublin 9, Ireland.

^dInstitute of Organic Chemistry and Macromolecular Chemistry, Friedrich Schiller University Jena, Humboldtstraße 10, 07743 Jena, Germany.

^eSaperatec GmbH, Ernst-Graebe-Straße 10, 33611 Bielefeld, Germany.

^fCenter for Energy and Environmental Chemistry Jena (CEEC Jena), Friedrich Schiller University Jena, Philosophenweg 7a, 07743 Jena, Germany

*Corresponding author: benjamin.dietzek@leibniz-ipht.de

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1 Optical characterization

Figure S1. UV-vis spectra taken of monomeric complexes 4 and 5, and Ru-PMMA polymer (PS) illustrating preserved MLCT absorption envelopes.

For global analysis, we employ Origin 2019 using the protocol, which is mentioned below:
We use the standard equation for the bi-exponential fit:

$$y = A_1 * \exp\left(-x/t_1\right) + A_2 * \exp\left(-x/t_2\right) + y_0$$

The standard equation for the mono-exponential fit is given below:

$$y = A_1 * \exp\left(x/t_1\right) + y_0$$

The iteration algorithm is based on Levenberg Marquardt, a maximum of 400 iteration is iterated to converge the spectra until Chi-Square tolerance value of $1E^{-9}$ and $COD(R^2) > 0.95$ are reached. All the transient absorption decays (Δ absorbance vs. time) share the parameters (t_1 , t_2) i.e. all decay transients are fitted with same lifetimes, A (which is a function of the probe wavelength) is associated with the decay associated spectra (DAS) as shown below.

Figure S2. Decay associated spectra (normalized) of (A) **MS**, (B) **PS**, (C) **M-50**, and (D) **P-50**.

Figure S3. (A) Nanosecond transient absorption spectra of $50 \mu\text{M}$ DPA in deaerated acetonitrile, excitation wavelength is 410 nm . (B) Corresponding decay associated spectrum (DAS). The triplet state formation in DPA $50 \mu\text{M}$ sample is due to intersystem crossing.

Pump-intensity dependent transient absorption decay transients of **MS** and **PS** are shown below. The transient absorption kinetics is measured at 380 nm , i.e. probing the ESA of the sensitizer units.

Figure 2: Transient decay of sensitizer (normalized) at different excitation power densities, line and symbol represent the measured data and dashed line represent mono-exponential decay fit. τ represents the triplet lifetime of the individual species as indicated in the subscript. (A) **MS**, at 0.2 mJ, fit reveals lifetime $\tau_{\text{MS}} = 4.5 \mu\text{s}$ (B) **MS**, $\tau_{\text{MS}} = 4.5 \mu\text{s}$, $4.5 \mu\text{s}$, $4.2 \mu\text{s}$ and $4.2 \mu\text{s}$ for the energy levels 0.1 mJ, 0.2 mJ, 0.5 mJ and 0.8 mJ respectively. (C) **PS** at 0.2 mJ, $\tau_{\text{PS}} = 2.5 \mu\text{s}$ (D) **PS**, $\tau_{\text{PS}} = 2.4 \mu\text{s}$, $2.5 \mu\text{s}$, $2.3 \mu\text{s}$ and $2.4 \mu\text{s}$ for the energy levels 0.1 mJ, 0.2 mJ, 0.5 mJ and 0.8 mJ respectively. Maximum error is within 10% of the given value.

We have investigated the **MS** and **PS** for 0.1 mJ, 0.2 mJ, 0.5 mJ and 0.8 mJ and find lifetimes centered around $4.4 \mu\text{s}$ and $2.4 \mu\text{s}$ for **MS** and **PS**, respectively. In particular, there is no significant change in the lifetime of either of the sensitizers in the range of concentration and pulse energy levels we employed. The higher limit of pulse energy is 0.8 mJ given the constraints of our experiment.

We do not observe any pump-intensity dependent changes of the excited-state lifetime; hence, we conclude that S-S TTA does not contribute to the excited-state decay path, neither in **MS** or **PS**.

2 Synthesis and Instrumentation

2.1 Preparation of the molecular sensitizer (**MS**)

All materials were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Merck) or Fluorochem (UK) and were used without further purification. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a 400 or 600 MHz Bruker spectrometer as indicated. The spectra were processed using Bruker Topspin software and were

calibrated against solvent peaks according to published values. High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (HR-MS) was performed at the HR-MS facility, Trinity College Dublin.

The ligand dqpCOOEt the dqpOH and the *mer*-[Ru(dqp)(CH₃CN)₃](PF₆)₂.¹⁻⁴ precursor complex were prepared according to methods previously reported. The preparation of the statistical copolymer Ru-PMMA was reported earlier and is reproduced in the following:

Synthesis of *mer*-[Ru(dqp)(dqp-COOH)](PF₆)₂

mer-[Ru(dqp)(CH₃CN)₃](PF₆)₂ (250 mg, 0.29 mmol) and dqpCOOEt (132 mg, 0.33 mmol) were heated at reflux in ethylene glycol (15 mL) for 72 hours. The deep-red reaction mixture was cooled and poured on a stirring solution of NH₄PF₆ to precipitate crude [Ru(dqp)(dqpCOOEt)](PF₆)₂ which was filtered and washed with water. The Ru-ester material was partially purified by dissolution in acetone (30 mL), filtering out insoluble solids, and evaporation of the red filtrate to provide a dry residue. Next, dried crude [Ru(dqp)(dqpCOOEt)](PF₆)₂ was suspended at room temperature in a mixture of 4:1 THF:CH₃OH (50 mL) and was treated with a solution of LiOH.H₂O (126 mg, 3.0 mmol) in 10 mL water. The combined reaction mixture was stirred overnight in the dark. Upon completion, the reaction volume was concentrated and a red solid was isolated by filtration after the addition of NH₄PF₆ in 1 M HCl (aq.) (50 mL). The crude Ru-acid material was purified by column chromatography on silica gel using 90/10/1 CH₃CN/H₂O/KNO₃ (20% aq.) as eluent. *mer*-[Ru(dqp)(dqpCOOH)](PF₆)₂ was isolated from the dried deep-red product band by twice precipitating a solid from acetone solutions using NH₄PF₆ in 1 M HCl (aq.). Yield: red solid, 146 mg (45 %). ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CD₃CN) δ (ppm): 7.01 (dd, 2H); 7.06 (dd, 2H); 7.44 (q, 4H); 7.65 (2d, 4H); 7.70 (d, 2H); 7.80 (d, 2H); 7.87 (d, 2H); 8.03 – 8.05 (m, 6H); 8.08 (d, 2H); 8.15 (t, 1H); 8.30 (s, 2H). ¹³C NMR (CD₃CN) δ (ppm): 122.69, 123.07, 127.52, 127.58, 127.65, 127.91, 128.61, 128.81, 131.06, 131.51, 132.77, 133.32, 133.82, 133.94, 138.37, 138.43, 138.96, 147.49, 147.57, 157.22, 157.81, 159.19, 159.62, 166.48. HR-MS (ESI(+)-qTOF) *m/z*: 812.1470 [M – 2PF₆]⁺; Calculated for C₄₇H₃₀N₆O₂Ru: 812.1474.

Synthesis of *mer*-[Ru(dqp)(dqpCOOEt)](PF₆)₂ (MS)

Purified *mer*-[Ru(dqp)(dqpCOOH)](PF₆)₂ (100 mg) was suspended in 10 mL of ethanol and treated with three drops of concentrated sulfuric acid. The mixture was heated at reflux overnight, then cooled and poured onto 100 mL of an aqueous NH₄PF₆ solution to precipitate *mer*-[Ru(dqp)(dqpCOOEt)](PF₆)₂ in quantitative yield. NMR analysis matches to literature report of the same complex.¹⁻⁴ ¹H NMR (600 MHz, Acetone-d₆) δ (ppm): 8.46 (d, 2H), 8.43 (d, 2H), 8.38 (s, 2H), 8.35 (t, 1H), 8.31 (d, 4H), 8.15 (d, 2H), 8.03 (d, 2H), 7.98 (d, 2H), 7.89 (dd, 4H), 7.61 (m, 4H), 7.27 (q, 4H), 4.47 (m, 2H), 1.39 (t, 3H).

2.2 Preparation of the polymer-based sensitizer (PS)

The synthesis and drawing were reproduced from Marcus Schulze (Diploma Thesis “Ruthenium(II) 2,6-di(quinolin-8'-yl)pyridine and polymeric structures”, FSU Jena, 25th October 2011) to warrant for accessible synthetic procedures (see Scheme SX), instrumentation and analytical characterization.

Scheme S1. Schematic representation of the synthetic approach towards PS (Ru-PMMA) illustrating intermediates.

2.2.1 Instrumentation and Materials

Starting materials were purchased from commercial sources and used as obtained unless otherwise noted. Solvents (dichloromethane, MeCN, toluene and THF) were dried with PureSolv-ENTTM Solvent Purification System (Innovative Technology). DMF was distilled over CaH₂ and stored over mol sieves (A3). TEA was dried over potassium hydroxide and distilled under argon. 3-Bromopropan-1-ol, methacryloyl chloride, MMA were distilled prior to use. AIBN was recrystallized from ethanol. 8-quinoline boronic acid and [Ru(dqp)(MeCN)₃](PF₆)₂ were prepared according to literature procedures.

Gel filtrations and non-flash chromatographic separations were performed on silica (SiO₂ 60, 0.040 to 0.063 mm, Merck KGaA) or aluminum oxide (neutral, 0.063 to 0.200 mm, Macherey & Nagel). For thin-layer chromatography (TLC) aluminum sheets precoated with silica gel 60 F254 (Merck) or aluminum oxide 60 F254 neutral (Merck) were used. Preparative size-exclusion chromatography was executed on Bio-Rad Bio-Beads S-X1 (mesh size: 200-400, molar mass operation range: 600 to 14,000 g/mol) swollen with DMF.

Anion exchange to the counter ion hexafluorophosphate was always performed in the same way: addition of ammonium hexafluorophosphate, filtration of the precipitate and washing with H₂O and diethyl ether. The crystallization of ruthenium(II) complexes were done by diffusion of diethyl ether into MeCN solution of the complex.

NMR spectra were recorded on a 250, 300, 400 or 600 MHz NMR spectrometer (Bruker AVANCE) in deuterated solvents at 25 °C. Chemical shifts are reported in parts per million (ppm, δ scale) relative to the residual solvent signal.

MALDI-TOF MS spectra have been measured on an Ultraflex III TOF/TOF (Bruker Daltonics GmbH) equipped with a Nd:YAG laser and a collision cell. All spectra were measured in the positive reflector mode using dithranol as a matrix. In addition, (HR) ESI-TOF MS spectrometry was performed on an ESI-(Q)-TOF-MS MICROTOF II (Bruker Daltonics) mass spectrometer.

Elemental analyses were carried out on a λ EuroVector EuroEA3000 elemental analyzer.

UV/Vis absorption spectra were measured on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 45 UV/VIS spectrophotometer.

Electrochemical measurements were performed on a Metrohm Autolab PGSTAT30 potentiostat with a standard three-electrode configuration using a graphite-disk working electrode, a platinum-rod auxiliary electrode and an Ag/AgCl reference electrode; scan rates from 20 to 1,000 mV/s were applied. The experiments were carried out in degassed MeCN (spectroscopy grade) containing tetra-*n*-butylammonium hexafluorophosphate salt (0.1 M). Ferrocene (Fc) was added at the end of each experiment as an internal standard. The potentials are quoted *vs.* the Fc/Fc⁺ couple.

GC-MS measurements were performed on the Shimadzu GCMS-2010 (carrier gas: helium; detector: mass spectrometer; column: Ultra Alloy Capillary Column UAC-5 (30 m length, 0.25 mm inner diameter, 0.25 μ m film thickness, (5% phenyl) methylpolysiloxane)). GC spectra were measured on the Shimadzu GC-2010 (carrier gas: helium; detector: flame ionization with hydrogen and air as detector gases; column: Restek Rtx-5 (30 m length, 0.25 mm inner diameter, 0.25 μ m film thickness, 5% diphenyl polysiloxane 95% dimethyl polysiloxane)).

Size-exclusion chromatography results were obtained by two different systems: 1.) Waters system (degasser: DG-980-50, pump: HPLC 1515, oven: Column Heater 1500, UV/Vis-detector: PDA detector 2996, RI-detector: RID 2414, eluent: DMAc + 0.08% NH₄PF₆, flow rate: 1 mL/min, temperature: 50 °C, column: Waters pre/Phenomenex Phenogel 103 Å/105 Å, separation range: 1,000 to 1,000,000 g/mol). 2.) Shimadzu system (controller: SCL-10A VP, degasser: DGU-14A, pump: LC-10AD VP, auto sampler: SIL-10AD VP, oven: Techlab, UV-detector: SPD-10AD VP, RI-detector: RID-10A, eluent: chloroform/*iso*-propanol/TEA [94:2:4], flow rate: 1 mL/min, temperature: 40 °C, column: PSS SDV pre/lin S, separation range: 100 to 150,000 g/mol).

Flash column chromatography was conducted on a Biotage Isolera One System using Biotage SNAP Cartridges KP-Sil and a UV/Vis detector. Microwave reactions were performed in the Biotage Initiator Sixty Microwave synthesizer.

2.2.2 Synthesis protocols

2,6-Dichloroisonicotinic acid ethyl ester

To a solution of 2,6 dichloroisonicotinic acid (10 g, 52 mmol) in ethanol (150 mL) was added concentrated sulfuric acid (20 mL). The mixture was refluxed for 4.5 h and was poured afterwards on crushed ice (200 g). A white precipitation was formed which was dissolved in chloroform. The organic phase was extracted with saturated sodium hydrogen carbonate solution. After drying over sodium sulfate and evaporation of the solvent 10.5 g (91%) of a white solid were obtained.

¹H NMR (300 MHz, chloroform-*d*₁): δ = 7.81 (s, 2H, H³), 4.43 (q, *J* = 7.16 Hz, 2H, -CH₂CH₃), 1.42 (t, *J* = 7.20 Hz, 3H, -CH₂CH₃) ppm. MS (GC-MS): *m/z* = 219 ([M]⁺), 191 ([M-C₂H₄]⁺), 174 ([M-CH₃CH₂O]⁺), 146 ([M-CH₃CH₂COO]⁺).

2,6-Dichloro-4-hydroxymethylpyridine

2,6-Dichloroisonicotinic acid ethyl ester (1.15 g, 5.24 mmol) and sodium borohydride (1.19 g, 31.47 mmol) were dissolved in THF (25 mL). The suspension was stirred for 15 min (strong bubbling) and afterwards MeOH (8 mL) were added dropwise over 30 min. After 3.5 h **21** was fully converted (GC-MS). Remaining sodium borohydride was destroyed by quenching with saturated ammonium chloride solution (10 mL) and stirring for 4 h. The water phase was extracted with ethyl acetate. This organic solution was dried over sodium sulfate and afterwards the solvent was evaporated to yield 933 mg (100%) of a white solid.

^1H NMR (300 MHz, chloroform- d_1): δ = 7.29 (s, 2H, H³), 4.76 (s, 2H, H^A), 2.19 (br. s., 2H, OH) ppm. MS (GC-MS): m/z = 177 ([M]⁺), 142 ([M-Cl]⁺).

2,6-Di(quinolin-8'-yl)-4-hydroxymethyl pyridine (1)

2,6-Dichloro-4-hydroxymethylpyridine (416 mg, 2.24 mmol), 8-quinoline boronic acid, 1.02 g, 5.84 mmol, Pd(dba)₂ (65 mg, 0.11 mmol), S-Phos (93 mg, 0.23 mmol) and potassium carbonate (1.56 g, 11.9 mmol) were dissolved in a mixture of H₂O (5 mL) and MeCN (10 mL). The microwave vial was degassed and heated to 130 °C for 3 h in the microwave. Afterwards, the solution was additionally stirred for 1 h in ethyl acetate. The mixture was extracted with ethyl acetate. After drying with sodium sulfate the crude product was adsorbed on silica and purified by flash column chromatography (hexane/ethyl acetate gradient) to give 653 mg (77%) of a slight yellow product which can be recrystallized from ethanol.

^1H NMR (250 MHz, dichloromethane- d_2): δ = 8.94 (dd, J = 4.33, 1.86 Hz, 2H, H²), 8.28 (dd, J = 8.45, 1.86 Hz, 2H, H⁴), 8.17 (dd, J = 7.01, 1.65 Hz, 2H, H⁷), 8.00 (s, 2H, H³), 7.93 (dd, J = 8.25, 1.65 Hz, 2H, H⁵), 7.67 (t, J = 7.42 Hz, 2H, H⁶), 7.47 (dd, J = 8.25, 4.54 Hz, 2H, H³), 4.85 (s, 2H, H^A), 3.30 (br. s., 1H, OH) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (63 MHz, dichloromethane- d_2): δ = 156.9, 150.2, 149.0, 145.9, 139.3, 136.5, 131.1, 128.7, 128.6, 126.3, 123.1, 121.1, 63.9 ppm. Elem. anal. calcd. for C₂₄H₁₇N₃O (363.14): C, 79.32%; H, 4.72%; N, 11.56%; found: C, 79.18%; H, 4.59%; N, 11.72%. UV/Vis (MeCN): λ_{max} ($\epsilon/\text{L}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$) = 303 (10,000), 209 (37,000) nm.

3-Bromopropyl-*tert*-butyl(dimethyl)silyl ether (2)

3-Bromo propan-1-ol (3 g, 21.7 mmol), TEA (2.56 g, 25.3 mmol) and *N,N*-dimethyl-4-aminopyridine (310 mg, 2.54 mmol) were dissolved in dry dichloromethane (33 mL) and cooled to 0 °C. To the solution was slowly added *tert*-butyl(dimethyl)silyl chloride (2.67 g, 17.7 mmol) over 30 min. After 3 h stirring the reaction mixture was quenched with H₂O and stirred for 10 min. The mixture was extracted with dichloromethane. A gel filtration of the crude product adsorbed on silica with hexane gave 3.35 g (75%) of a colorless liquid.

^1H NMR (300 MHz, chloroform- d_1): δ = 3.71 (t, J = 5.71 Hz, 2H, H^C), 3.48 (t, J = 6.40 Hz, 2H, H^A), 2.00 (quin, J = 6.00 Hz, 2H, H^B), 0.88 (s, 9H, Si-C(CH₃)), 0.05 (s, 6H, Si-CH₃) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, chloroform- d_1): δ = 60.3, 35.6, 30.3, 25.9, 18.2, -5.4 ppm. MS (GC-MS): m/z = 195 ([M-C(CH₃)₃]⁺), 167 ([M-C₆H₁₃]⁺), 137 ([M-TBDMS]⁺), 115 (TBDMS)⁺.

2,6-Di(quinolin-8'-yl)-4-[3-(tert-butyldimethylsilyloxy)propoxymethyl]pyridine (3)

1 (300 mg, 0.83 mmol) and a 60% dispersion of sodium hydride in mineral oil (40 mg, 1 mmol) were dissolved in dry DMF and stirred for 15 min. **2** (510 mg, 2.02 mmol) was added to the mixture. After stirring for 17 h at room temperature additional 1 eq. of sodium hydride and twice 1 eq. of **2** were added. The reaction was stirred 2 h after the last addition and then quenched with H₂O (20 mL). Afterwards the solution was extracted with dichloromethane and the organic phase was extracted extensively with brine and H₂O. The crude product was dried over magnesium sulfate, adsorbed on silica and purified by flash column chromatography (hexane/ethyl acetate 2:1) to yield 385 mg (87%) of the solid product.

¹H NMR (300 MHz, chloroform-*d*): δ = 8.97 (d, *J* = 2.97 Hz, 2H, H²), 8.36 (d, *J* = 6.85 Hz, 2H, H⁴), 8.28 (d, *J* = 8.22 Hz, 2H, H⁷), 8.19 (s, 2H, H³), 7.92 (d, *J* = 7.99 Hz, 2H, H⁵), 7.70 (t, *J* = 7.65 Hz, 2H, H⁶), 7.50 (dd, *J* = 8.11, 4.00 Hz, 2H, H³), 4.84 (s, 2H, H^A), 3.70 - 3.80 (m, 4H, H^{B,D}), 1.89 (quin, *J* = 6.22 Hz, 2H, H^C), 0.86 (s, 9H, Si-(C(CH₃)₃), 0.01 (s, 6H, Si-CH₃) ppm. MS (GC-MS): *m/z* = 361 ([M-HO(CH₂)₃OTBMDS]⁺), 322 ([M-CH₂O(CH₂)₃OTBMDS]⁺).

2,6-Di(quinolin-8'-yl)-4-[3-(hydroxy)propoxymethyl]pyridine (3)

2 (444 mg, 0.83 mmol) was dissolved in dry THF (12 mL). To the solution TBAF·3H₂O (tetra-*n*-butylammonium fluoride trihydrate, 782 mg, 2.48 mmol) was added and afterwards stirred for 3 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was treated with H₂O and dichloromethane and the organic phase was separated. The water phase was extracted extensively with dichloromethane and ethyl acetate. After a gel filtration (gradient ethyl acetate to ethyl acetate/MeOH 4:1) 333 mg (95%) of the slightly yellow product were obtained.

¹H NMR (300 MHz, MeCN-*d*₃): δ = 8.94 (d, *J* = 4.11 Hz, 2H, H²), 8.37 (d, *J* = 8.22 Hz, 2H, H⁴), 8.20 (d, *J* = 7.08 Hz, 2H, H⁷), 8.06 (s, 2H, H³), 8.00 (d, *J* = 8.22 Hz, 2H, H⁵), 7.70 (t, *J* = 7.65 Hz, 2H, H⁶), 7.53 (dd, *J* = 8.34, 4.23 Hz, 2H, H³), 4.70 (s, 2H, H^A), 3.69 (t, *J* = 6.28 Hz, 2H, H^B), 3.64 (t, *J* = 6.28 Hz, 2H, H^D), 2.31 (br. s., 1H, OH), 1.81 (quin, *J* = 6.21 Hz, 2H, H^C) ppm. ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, MeCN-*d*₃): □ = 156.6, 150.4, 146.7, 145.7, 138.9, 136.5, 131.0, 128.9, 128.7, 126.3, 123.7, 121.4, 71.2, 67.9, 58.9, 32.6 ppm. MS (ESI): *m/z* = 422.2 ([M+H]⁺). HR-MS (ESI): calcd. M ([C₂₇H₂₃N₃O₂+H]⁺): 422.1863; found: 422.1853 g/mol; error: 2.4 ppm. UV/Vis (MeCN): λ_{max} (ε/L·mol⁻¹·cm⁻¹) = 305 (15,000), 228 (46,000) nm.

[[2,6-Di(quinolin-8'-yl)pyridine][2,6-di(quinolin-8'-yl)-4-[3-(hydroxy)propoxymethyl]pyridine]ruthenium(II) hexafluorophosphate (4)

3 (293 mg, 0.70 mmol) and ([Ru(dqp)(MeCN)₃](PF₆)₂, 539 mg, 0.64 mmol) were dissolved in ethylene glycol (15 mL). The mixture was heated to 120 °C and stirred for 1 day under a constant nitrogen stream. After cooling and anion exchange with ammonium hexafluorophosphate a red precipitation was obtained.

2 PF₆⁻ The enrichment of the *mer* complexes was achieved by fractionated crystallization. Afterwards the chosen fractions were purified by column chromatography (MeCN/H₂O/sat. KNO₃ 40:4:1). After the anion exchange 639 mg of a red solid were dissolved in a mixture of MeCN (290 mL) and H₂O (230 mL). The solution was purged for 10 min with nitrogen and then potassium carbonate (286 mg, 2.07 mmol) was added. The reaction mixture was neutralized with concentrated hydrochloride acid (172 □L) and

extracted with dichloromethane. 387 mg (53%) of product **4** were obtained after a further column chromatography and crystallization.

^1H NMR (300 MHz, MeCN- d_3): δ = 8.16 (t, J = 7.99 Hz, 1H, H⁴), 8.07 (d, J = 7.08 Hz, 8H, H^{2',4'}), 7.88 (d, J = 7.99 Hz, 2H, H³), 7.84 (s, 2H, H^{3''}), 7.66 - 7.77 (m, 8H, H^{5',7'}), 7.45 (t, J = 7.77 Hz, 4H, H⁶), 7.01 - 7.18 (m, 4H, H³), 4.73 (s, 2H, H^A), 3.60 - 3.93 (m, 4H, H^{B,D}), 2.62 (t, J = 5.25 Hz, 1H, OH), 1.83 (quin, J = 6.28 Hz, 2H, H^C) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, MeCN- d_3): δ = 158.5, 156.8, 156.5, 151.1, 146.6, 146.5, 138.1, 137.6, 137.5, 133.0, 131.8, 131.8, 130.6, 127.9, 126.8, 126.8, 126.6, 126.6, 125.7, 122.0, 121.9, 70.0, 68.1, 58.6, 32.5 ppm. MS (ESI): m/z = 428.1 ([M-2PF₆]²⁺). HR-MS (ESI): calcd. M ([C₅₀H₃₈N₆O₂Ru-2PF₆]²⁺): 428.1051; found: 428.1054 g/mol; error: 0.7 ppm. UV/Vis (MeCN): λ_{max} ($\epsilon/\text{L}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$) = 493 (16,000), 335 (31,000), 237 (69,000), 208 (103,000) nm. CV (MeCN, 1 M TBAPF₆): E_{1/2} ($\square E_p/\text{mV}$) = 0.69 (60), -1.74 (60), -1.87 (110), -2.36 (irreversible) V vs. Fc/Fc⁺.

[[2,6-Di(quinolin-8'-yl)pyridine][2,6-di(quinolin-8'-yl)-4-[3-(methacrylate)propoxymethyl]pyridine]ruthenium(II)] hexafluorophosphate (5)

4 (371 mg, 0.30 mmol) was dissolved in a mixture of dry dichloromethane (50 mL) and dry MeCN (5 mL) and cooled to 0 °C. Afterwards TEA (650 \square L, 4.69 mmol) and *N,N*-dimethyl-4-aminopyridine (56 mg, 0.46 mmol) were firstly added and then methacryloyl chloride (294 \square L, 3.03 mmol) in two portions. After stirring for 30 h at room temperature the mixture was quenched with

H₂O. Ammonium hexafluorophosphate was added and the organic phase was separated and washed twice with hydrochloride acid (100 mL, pH = 3), twice with sodium carbonate solution (100 mL, pH = 11) and twice with H₂O (100 mL). This crude product was further purified by column chromatography to obtain 272 mg (74%) of **5**.

^1H NMR (300 MHz, MeCN- d_3): δ = 8.17 (t, J = 8.45 Hz, 1H, H⁴), 8.03 - 8.11 (m, 8H, H^{2',4'}), 7.89 (d, J = 8.22 Hz, 2H, H³), 7.83 (s, 2H, H^{3''}), 7.66 - 7.76 (m, 8H, H^{5',7'}), 7.46 (t, J = 7.88 Hz, 4H, H⁶), 7.05 (dd, J = 7.65, 5.60 Hz, 4H, H³), 5.97 (s, 1H, H^E), 5.49 (s, 1H, H^E), 4.72 (s, 2H, H^A), 4.26 (t, J = 6.40 Hz, 2H, H^D), 3.72 (t, J = 6.05 Hz, 2H, H^B), 2.02 (quin, J = 6.40 Hz, 2H, H^C), 1.83 (s, 3H, Me) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, MeCN- d_3): δ = 167.0, 158.5, 158.4, 156.9, 156.5, 151.0, 146.6, 146.6, 138.2, 137.6, 137.6, 136.7, 133.0, 131.9, 131.8, 130.7, 130.6, 128.0, 126.9, 126.7, 126.7, 125.7, 124.7, 122.0, 122.0, 70.1, 67.7, 67.5, 61.6, 28.8, 17.4 ppm. MS (ESI): m/z = 462.1 ([M-2PF₆]²⁺). HR-MS (ESI): calcd. M ([C₅₄H₄₂N₆O₃Ru-2PF₆]²⁺): 462.1183; found: 462.1198 g/mol; error: 3.5 ppm. MS (MALDI, dithranol): m/z = 924.1 ([M-PF₆]⁺). UV/Vis (MeCN): λ_{max} ($\epsilon/\text{L}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$) = 494 (13,500), 335 (27,000), 237 (63,000), 206 (97,000) nm. CV (MeCN, 1 M TBAPF₆): E_{1/2} ($\square E_p/\text{mV}$) = 0.71 (80), -1.68 (60), -1.91 (70), -2.42 (irreversible), -2.62 (irreversible) V vs. Fc/Fc⁺.

Poly(MMA-*stat*-[Ru(dqp)(dqpCH₂O(CH₂)₃OMA)]²⁺) (PS)

The following stock solutions were prepared: CPDB (26.06 mg to 2 mL DMF) and AIBN (8.03 mg to 2 mL DMF). To a mixture of MMA (132.1 mg, 1.32 mmol) and **5** (84.8 mg, 0.07 mmol) the volumes of CPDB solution, AIBN solution and DMF (**Table S1**) were added. The microwave vial was capped, a t_0 -sample was taken and afterwards degassed for 30 min. Then, the prepared sample was heated to 70 °C in an oil bath for 16 h. After the reaction, the monomers were separated by a preparative size-exclusion chromatography (SX-1, DMF) and the resulting polymer was precipitated in diethyl ether and dried to yield 95 mg (44%) of a red

powder.

Table S1 Synthesis conditions for Poly(MMA-*stat*-[Ru(dqp)(dqpCH₂O(CH₂)₃OMA)]²⁺) (PS)

	Ratio MMA/5	Ratio monomer/CPDB/AIBN	c (total monomer) [M]	V _{AIBN} [μ L]	V _{CPDB} [μ L]	V _{DMF} [μ L]
PS	95/5	100/4/1	2	143	238	319

GC: 85% conversion of MMA. SEC (DMAc, 0.08% NH₄PF₆, PDA detector ($\lambda_{\text{det}} = 450$ nm) PMMA standard): 79% conversion of **5**, $M_n = 22,000$ g/mol, PDI = 1.24. ¹H NMR (600 MHz, delay time = 10 s dichloromethane-*d*₂): $\delta = 8.11$ (s, 1H, H⁴), 7.86 - 8.02 (m, 8H, H^{2',4'}) 7.55 - 7.82 (m, 12H, H^{3,3',5',7'}), 7.38 - 7.47 (m, 4H, H⁶), 6.99 - 7.11 (m, 4H, H^{3'}), 4.66 - 4.79 (m, 2H, H^A), 4.01 (s, 2H, H^D), 3.67 (s, 2H, H^B), 3.50 (s, 49H, methyl ester group of MMA) 0.55 - 2.01 (m, 105H, PMMA backbone and H^C) ppm, **5** content = 6.1%: . MS (ESI): $M_n = 8,000$ g/mol. UV/Vis (MeCN): λ_{max} ($\epsilon/L \cdot \text{mol}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$) = 494 (13,800), 334 (28,500), 238 (65,000), 209 (96,000) nm. CV (MeCN, 1 M TBAPF₆): $E_{1/2}$ ($\square E_p/mV$) = 0.71 (60), -1.72 (65), -1.91 (120), -2.41 (irreversible) V vs. Fc/Fc⁺.

2.3 NMR spectra

Figure S4. ^1H NMR Spectrum (600 MHz, CD_3CN) of $\text{mer-}[\text{Ru}(\text{dqp})(\text{dqpCOOH})](\text{PF}_6)_2$ with insets to show regions of interest above the full spectrum.

Figure S5. ^{13}C NMR Spectrum (150 MHz, CD_3CN) of $\text{mer-}[\text{Ru}(\text{dqp})(\text{dqpCOOH})](\text{PF}_6)_2$ to show region of interest.

Figure S6. ^1H NMR Spectrum (600 MHz, Acetone- d_6) of *mer*-[Ru(dqp)(dqpCOOEt)](PF $_6$) $_2$ (MS) with insets to show regions of interest above the full spectrum.

Figure S7. ^1H NMR spectrum (300 MHz, CD_3CN) of monomer complex [Ru(dqp)(dqpCH $_2$ O(CH $_2$) $_3$ OMA)] $^{2+}$ (5).

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